

Internship proposal: Estimation of retinal Windkessel RC, normalised compliance/resistance indices, and artery–vein lag from Doppler holography pulse-wave analysis

Contact: micatlan@gmail.com

January 8, 2026

1 Objective and scope

We aim to estimate pressure-free, bed-level dynamics of the retinal vascular bed at the optic disc from beat-resolved measurements of total arterial inflow $Q_A(t)$ and total venous outflow $Q_V(t)$ (or alternatively the average velocity waveforms in selected arterial and venous segments). We focus on the two-element Windkessel (WK2) time constant $\tau = RC$, while explicitly allowing for a small artery-to-vein lag Δt (physiologic transit and/or measurement timing). Throughout, estimates are computed per beat (or per short window spanning a few beats), then aggregated robustly (e.g. weighted median) across accepted beats/windows using QC-derived weights.

2 Delay + two-element Windkessel (RC): frequency-domain identification

2.1 Model: delay + first-order low-pass transfer

Starting from the pressure-free WK2 relation

$$Q_V(t) + \tau \dot{Q}_V(t) = Q_A(t), \quad \tau = RC, \quad (1)$$

we include a pure delay Δt between measured waveforms via the transfer

$$H(\omega) \equiv \frac{Q_V(\omega)}{Q_A(\omega)} \approx k \frac{e^{-i\omega\Delta t}}{1 + i\omega\tau}, \quad (2)$$

where k is an optional constant gain (often set to $k \simeq 1$ after band-limited normalisation of Q_A and Q_V in the cardiac band).

2.2 Beat segmentation and phase-normalised resampling (fixed samples per cycle)

Why resample. Because the cardiac period varies from beat to beat, we convert each accepted beat into a *phase-normalised* representation with the same number of samples per cycle. This makes the harmonic extraction well-defined (integer harmonics), improves numerical stability, and enables robust aggregation across beats/windows.

Beat anchors: maximum systolic upstroke points. We segment beats using anchor times $\{t_k\}$ defined by the maximum systolic upstroke in the arterial inflow, i.e.

$$t_k \equiv \arg \max_{t \in \mathcal{W}_k} \frac{dQ_A(t)}{dt}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{W}_k is a search window around the expected systolic upstroke (obtained from a band-limited derivative of Q_A for example). Using the peak of dQ_A/dt provides a sharp, reproducible timing marker that is less sensitive to dirotic features than peak-finding on Q_A .

Per-beat period and phase. Define the k -th beat interval and duration as

$$\mathcal{I}_k = [t_k, t_{k+1}), \quad T_k = t_{k+1} - t_k, \quad (4)$$

and the phase variable $\phi \in [0, 1)$ by $\phi = (t - t_k)/T_k$ for $t \in \mathcal{I}_k$.

Resampling to a fixed number of points. For each beat k , we resample both $Q_A(t)$ and $Q_V(t)$ onto a uniform phase grid $\phi_m = m/N$ with $m = 0, \dots, N - 1$:

$$Q_A^{(k)}[m] = Q_A(t_k + \phi_m T_k), \quad Q_V^{(k)}[m] = Q_V(t_k + \phi_m T_k). \quad (5)$$

We use band-limited interpolation (or cubic spline / linear interpolation after cardiac-band filtering) to achieve sub-sample accuracy while avoiding high-frequency artefacts.

Optional detrending / centring. To reduce sensitivity to slow drifts and offsets, we optionally subtract the per-beat mean (or a low-order trend) before harmonic extraction:

$$Q_A^{(k)}[m] \leftarrow Q_A^{(k)}[m] - \frac{1}{N} \sum_m Q_A^{(k)}[m], \quad Q_V^{(k)}[m] \leftarrow Q_V^{(k)}[m] - \frac{1}{N} \sum_m Q_V^{(k)}[m]. \quad (6)$$

QC for anchors and resampling. Beats are rejected if: (i) the upstroke derivative peak is ambiguous or multi-modal; (ii) T_k is outside physiologic bounds; (iii) the resampled waveform shows discontinuity at $m = 0/N$ (suggesting mis-segmentation); or (iv) rhythm is irregular (ectopy) such that phase normalisation would be misleading. Accepted beats provide the inputs for the harmonic transfer estimates below.

Link to harmonic-domain coefficients. On each resampled beat, the discrete Fourier series (DFS) coefficients are

$$Q_{A_n}^{(k)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{m=0}^{N-1} Q_A^{(k)}[m] e^{-i2\pi nm/N}, \quad Q_{V_n}^{(k)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{m=0}^{N-1} Q_V^{(k)}[m] e^{-i2\pi nm/N}, \quad (7)$$

corresponding to physical harmonic frequencies $\omega_{n,k} = 2\pi n/T_k$. These coefficients feed directly into the beat-resolved transfer $H_{n,k} = Q_{V_n}^{(k)}/Q_{A_n}^{(k)}$ and the weighted aggregation pipeline described next.

2.3 Beat-resolved harmonic transfer estimates

For each accepted beat (or short window), with cardiac period T and $\omega_1 = 2\pi/T$, compute complex Fourier coefficients at harmonics $n \in \mathcal{N}$:

$$Q_{A_n} \equiv Q_A(\omega_n), \quad Q_{V_n} \equiv Q_V(\omega_n), \quad \omega_n = n\omega_1, \quad (8)$$

and form the empirical transfer

$$H_n \equiv \frac{Q_{Vn}}{Q_{An}}. \quad (9)$$

Harmonics are retained via QC gates (e.g. coherence and harmonic SNR), and assigned weights w_n (larger for higher coherence/SNR). In practice, $\mathcal{N} = \{1, 2\}$ is often sufficient; higher harmonics can be included when QC permits.

2.4 Robust joint identification: grid-search Δt + closed-form τ

Principle (avoid phase unwrapping). We scan Δt over a narrow physiologic range on a fine grid (e.g. 1–2 ms step). For each candidate delay, we compute a closed-form weighted least-squares estimate of τ using the *complex* harmonic data (phase and magnitude), without requiring phase unwrapping.

Delay compensation. For a candidate Δt , define the de-delayed transfer

$$\tilde{H}_n(\Delta t) \equiv H_n e^{+i\omega_n \Delta t}. \quad (10)$$

One-parameter complex least squares for τ . With $k = 1$, we expect $\tilde{H}_n(\Delta t) \approx (1 + i\omega_n \tau)^{-1}$, equivalently

$$1 - \tilde{H}_n(\Delta t) \approx \tau (i\omega_n \tilde{H}_n(\Delta t)). \quad (11)$$

Let

$$a_n(\Delta t) \equiv i\omega_n \tilde{H}_n(\Delta t), \quad b_n(\Delta t) \equiv \tilde{H}_n(\Delta t). \quad (12)$$

Then the weighted LS estimate is

$$\hat{\tau}(\Delta t) = \frac{\Re(\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} w_n a_n^*(\Delta t) [1 - b_n(\Delta t)])}{\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} w_n |a_n(\Delta t)|^2}, \quad \hat{\tau}(\Delta t) \leftarrow \max(\hat{\tau}(\Delta t), 0). \quad (13)$$

Selecting Δt by minimal complex residual. For each Δt we compute

$$J(\Delta t) = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} w_n \left| 1 - (1 + i\omega_n \hat{\tau}(\Delta t)) \tilde{H}_n(\Delta t) \right|^2, \quad (14)$$

and select

$$\hat{\Delta t} = \arg \min_{\Delta t} J(\Delta t), \quad \hat{\tau} = \hat{\tau}(\hat{\Delta t}). \quad (15)$$

2.5 Optional gain correction k (linear update)

If a constant gain mismatch is suspected, retain k in (2). For a fixed $(\Delta t, \tau)$, the weighted complex LS estimate is

$$\hat{k}(\Delta t, \tau) = \frac{\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} w_n H_n \left(\frac{e^{-i\omega_n \Delta t}}{1 + i\omega_n \tau} \right)^*}{\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} w_n \left| \frac{e^{-i\omega_n \Delta t}}{1 + i\omega_n \tau} \right|^2}. \quad (16)$$

One may replace $J(\Delta t)$ by the residual using \hat{k} without changing the grid-search.

2.6 Per-harmonic estimators (after delay correction) and robust aggregation

After estimating $\widehat{\Delta t}$, define $\widetilde{H}_n \equiv H_n e^{i\omega_n \widehat{\Delta t}}$. Two derivative-free per-harmonic estimators are

$$\widehat{\tau}_{\phi,n} = -\frac{1}{\omega_n} \tan(\angle \widetilde{H}_n), \quad (17)$$

$$\widehat{\tau}_{|H|,n} = \frac{1}{\omega_n} \sqrt{\frac{1}{|\widetilde{H}_n|^2} - 1}. \quad (18)$$

We report τ as a robust aggregate across $n \in \mathcal{N}$ and beats/windows (weighted median with QC weights). When per-harmonic estimates disagree beyond tolerance, the WK2 block is suppressed rather than forced.

2.7 Pressure-free normalised indices

To compare across heart rates and sessions without absolute pressure, we report

$$C^* = \frac{\tau}{T}, \quad R^* = \frac{T}{\tau} = \frac{1}{C^*}, \quad (19)$$

with T the cardiac period estimated from $Q_A(t)$ (or $Q_V(t)$).

2.8 Quality control, reporting, and uncertainty

QC gates. Require: (i) sufficient accepted beats N_{beat} ; (ii) minimum harmonic coherence/SNR at $n \in \{1, 2\}$ (and any additional n used); and (iii) stability of $(\widehat{\Delta t}, \widehat{\tau})$ across beats/windows. If any gate fails (poor coherence, irregular rhythm, large dispersion), suppress the WK2 estimate.

Uncertainty. Estimate uncertainty for $(\Delta t, \tau, C^*, R^*)$ by block-bootstrap resampling over cardiac cycles (and windows if applicable), recomputing the full estimator (15) (and (16) if enabled) on each replicate.

Recommended outputs. Report $(\widehat{\Delta t}, \widehat{\tau}, C^*, R^*)$, N_{beat} , harmonic set \mathcal{N} , coherence/SNR summaries, and dispersion across beats (e.g. MAD or IQR). A diagnostic plot can compare measured H_n to the fitted transfer $ke^{-i\omega_n \Delta t}/(1 + i\omega_n \tau)$.

3 Time-domain identification (delay + WK2 ODE)

3.1 Shared delay bounds

Let the delay search interval be

$$\Delta t \in [\Delta t_{\min}, \Delta t_{\max}], \quad (20)$$

with grid step $\delta_{\Delta t}$ (e.g. 1–2 ms), identical to the frequency-domain grid in Sec. 2.4.

3.2 Model

We fit

$$Q_V(t) + \tau \dot{Q}_V(t) = Q_A(t - \Delta t), \quad \tau > 0, \quad (21)$$

where $Q_A(t - \Delta t)$ is obtained by band-limited interpolation (or Fourier-domain phase shift restricted to the cardiac band).

3.3 Default (robust): derivative-free integral form

Integrating (21) from t_0 to t yields

$$\int_{t_0}^t Q_V(s) ds + \tau(Q_V(t) - Q_V(t_0)) = \int_{t_0}^t Q_A(s - \Delta t) ds. \quad (22)$$

Define

$$S_V(t) \equiv \int_{t_0}^t Q_V(s) ds, \quad S_A(t; \Delta t) \equiv \int_{t_0}^t Q_A(s - \Delta t) ds. \quad (23)$$

Then, for fixed Δt ,

$$S_A(t; \Delta t) - S_V(t) \approx \tau(Q_V(t) - Q_V(t_0)), \quad (24)$$

which is linear in τ and avoids differentiating Q_V .

Grid-search Δt + closed-form τ . For each candidate $\Delta t \in [\Delta t_{\min}, \Delta t_{\max}]$, estimate τ by weighted LS over samples t_k within the beat/window:

$$\hat{\tau}(\Delta t) = \frac{\sum_k w_k (Q_V(t_k) - Q_V(t_0)) (S_A(t_k; \Delta t) - S_V(t_k))}{\sum_k w_k (Q_V(t_k) - Q_V(t_0))^2}, \quad \hat{\tau}(\Delta t) \leftarrow \max(\hat{\tau}(\Delta t), 0), \quad (25)$$

and select

$$\widehat{\Delta t}_{\text{TD}} = \arg \min_{\Delta t \in [\Delta t_{\min}, \Delta t_{\max}]} J_{\text{TD}}(\Delta t), \quad \widehat{\tau}_{\text{TD}} = \hat{\tau}(\widehat{\Delta t}_{\text{TD}}), \quad (26)$$

with residual

$$J_{\text{TD}}(\Delta t) = \sum_k w_k (S_A(t_k; \Delta t) - S_V(t_k) - \hat{\tau}(\Delta t)(Q_V(t_k) - Q_V(t_0)))^2. \quad (27)$$

Implementation notes. Per-beat demeaning (or periodic boundary enforcement) improves robustness to slow drifts. Weights w_k can downweight low-SNR phases and enable robust M-estimation via IRLS. The integral form is preferred over direct differentiation in noisy data.

3.4 Optional: direct ODE residual fit (smoothed derivative)

As a secondary check,

$$\min_{\Delta t, \tau} \sum_k w_k \left(Q_V(t_k) + \tau \widehat{Q}_V(t_k) - Q_A(t_k - \Delta t) \right)^2, \quad (28)$$

where \widehat{Q}_V is obtained by a noise-robust differentiator (Savitzky–Golay, smoothing spline derivative, or band-limited differentiation in the cardiac band). This can be more sensitive to high-frequency noise than the integral form.

3.5 Aggregation and uncertainty

Compute $(\widehat{\Delta t}_{\text{TD}}, \widehat{\tau}_{\text{TD}})$ per beat/window and report robust aggregates across beats (weighted median). Uncertainty is obtained by block-bootstrap over beats. Large discrepancies between time-domain and frequency-domain estimates are treated as QC flags.

4 Advanced analysis (discrete-time system identification)

4.1 ARX as a discrete-time form of “delay + RC low-pass”

ARX (one-pole). We model venous outflow as a stable one-pole discrete-time system driven by arterial inflow:

$$Q_V[n] = a Q_V[n-1] + b Q_A[n-d] + \varepsilon[n], \quad (29)$$

where n indexes samples at spacing Δ (seconds), d is an integer input delay (samples), and $\varepsilon[n]$ is residual noise/mismatch.

Mapping to continuous time. For a first-order low-pass, the pole maps as

$$a = e^{-\Delta/\tau}, \quad \tau = -\frac{\Delta}{\ln a}, \quad 0 < a < 1, \quad (30)$$

and under exact discretisation with a zero-order-hold input, a physically consistent gain is

$$b \approx 1 - a \quad (\text{after cardiac-band amplitude normalisation of } Q_A, Q_V). \quad (31)$$

We enforce a shared delay bound by scanning

$$d \in [d_{\min}, d_{\max}], \quad d_{\min} = \left\lfloor \frac{\Delta t_{\min}}{\Delta} \right\rfloor, \quad d_{\max} = \left\lceil \frac{\Delta t_{\max}}{\Delta} \right\rceil. \quad (32)$$

4.2 Robust weighted LS with physical regularisation

Weighted LS fit. For fixed d , estimate (a, b) by weighted LS over valid sample indices n :

$$(\hat{a}, \hat{b}) = \arg \min_{a,b} \sum_n w_n (Q_V[n] - a Q_V[n-1] - b Q_A[n-d])^2, \quad (33)$$

omitting rows with missing samples. We select \hat{d} by minimal weighted residual over $d \in [d_{\min}, d_{\max}]$.

Optional physical tie $b \approx 1 - a$. When the data are ambiguous (low SNR), we optionally add a weak ridge penalty

$$\arg \min_{a,b} \sum_n w_n (\cdot)^2 + \lambda (b - (1 - a))^2, \quad (34)$$

with small λ .

Stability and outputs. We enforce stability by clamping \hat{a} to $(0, 1)$:

$$\hat{a} \leftarrow \text{clip}(\hat{a}; a_{\min}, a_{\max}), \quad 0 < a_{\min} < a_{\max} < 1, \quad \hat{\tau} = -\frac{\Delta}{\ln \hat{a}}, \quad (35)$$

and report $\hat{\Delta}t = \hat{d}\Delta$, $\hat{\tau}$, $C^* = \tau/T$, and $R^* = 1/C^*$, aggregated robustly across beats/windows.

4.3 Instrumental variables (IV) for bias reduction when Q_V is noisy

Why IV. Ordinary LS can be biased if regressors (e.g. $Q_V[n-1]$, $Q_A[n-d]$) correlate with noise $\varepsilon[n]$ (e.g. strong measurement noise in Q_V , or preprocessing-induced correlations). Instrumental variables (IV) mitigate this using *instruments* correlated with the true regressors but approximately uncorrelated with the output noise.

IV-ARX (two-stage least squares). Let $\varphi[n] = [Q_V[n-1] \ Q_A[n-d]]^\top$ and $\theta = [a \ b]^\top$. Choose an instrument vector $z[n]$ built from lagged and/or band-filtered versions of Q_A , e.g.

$$z[n] = [Q_A[n-d-1], Q_A[n-d-2], \widetilde{Q}_A[n-d]]^\top, \quad (36)$$

where \widetilde{Q}_A is a cardiac-band version of Q_A . Stack rows of Φ as $\varphi[n]^\top$, stack y as $Q_V[n]$, stack Z as $z[n]^\top$, and set $W = \text{diag}(w_n)$. Then the weighted 2SLS estimator is

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{IV}} = \left(\Phi^\top W Z (Z^\top W Z)^{-1} Z^\top W \Phi \right)^{-1} \Phi^\top W Z (Z^\top W Z)^{-1} Z^\top W y. \quad (37)$$

As above, we scan $d \in [d_{\min}, d_{\max}]$, enforce $0 < a < 1$, map $a \mapsto \tau$ via (30), and report $(\Delta t, \tau, C^*, R^*)$ with bootstrap confidence intervals.

QC for IV. We suppress IV outputs when instruments are weak (low correlation between z and φ) or when stability constraints are repeatedly violated in a window. Large discrepancies between IV-ARX, LS-ARX, and the frequency-domain estimator are treated as QC flags.

5 Open-source datasets and rendering pipelines

1. Dataset: [10.5281/zenodo.16761111](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761111).
2. Hologram rendering: [HoloDoppler](#).
3. Velocity/flow estimation: [EyeFlow](#).

6 Conclusion

We provide a coherent, pressure-free estimation toolkit for the WK2 time constant τ and its normalised indices C^* and R^* from beat-resolved $Q_A(t)$ and $Q_V(t)$, explicitly accounting for a small artery-to-vein delay Δt . The default harmonic-domain estimator is derivative-free and robust to phase issues (no unwrapping), while the integral time-domain estimator offers an independent, numerically stable cross-check. Optional ARX/IV-ARX variants provide fast discrete-time identification and additional robustness when data are gappy or when output noise biases ordinary least squares, enabling routine use in multicentre settings.